

BIOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF RESORBABLE COMPOSITE BONE FRACTURE REPAIR PLATES

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1 Introduction

Current bone repair implants for use within the body are made from metals [1, 2], which have disadvantages such as stress shielding and can remain in the body permanently. In addition, a fractured bone fixated with a metal plate may re-fracture upon removal of the implant [3]. This is due to the fact that bone does not carry sufficient load during the healing process. Recently, a move towards degradable composite materials for bone repair applications (to replace metal plate equivalents) has been viewed as extremely favourable [4, 5]. The main objective of these composite plates would be to degrade not only *in vivo* but also to take an active part in the tissue regeneration process.

The main advantage of having a material that degrades is so that an implant would not necessitate a second surgical event for removal. In addition, biodegradation may offer other advantages and an implant prepared from biodegradable materials could be engineered to degrade at a rate that would transfer load slowly to the healing bone.

Phosphate glasses and fibres are fully resorbable amorphous glass products that provide an alternative to silicate-based glasses, with comparable mechanical properties and with much lower energy manufacturing costs (phosphate glasses melt typically at lower than ~1100 °C, whilst silicate based glasses melt at close to 1500 °C). A particular added value of phosphate glasses is that their degradation rates can be varied very easily by several orders of magnitude, ranging from hours to days to months and even years [6]. The most common

and prevalent components in these glasses are calcium and phosphate ions, which are common constituents of the body and thus no adverse health issues or inflammatory responses are expected.

In this study, fully resorbable composite bone repair plates comprising a polylactic acid (PLA) matrix reinforced with phosphate glass fibres (PGF) were investigated. In addition, a stainless steel plate with the same dimension was utilised as a control group. Flexural and torsional properties of the two kinds of plates alone and plated rabbit tibia bones were tested via three point bending and torsion tests.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Animal model

Tibia bones were obtained from cadaveric New Zealand White rabbits at the age of 12 weeks. The bones were wrapped in towels and stored at -18°C. Before testing, the bones were thawed to room temperature. They were kept moist during testing.

2.2 Manufacturing process of composite plate

In this study, phosphate based glass of formulation 40P₂O₅– 16CaO – 24MgO – 16Na₂O – 4Fe₂O₃ (in mol%) was prepared from sodium dihydrogen phosphate (NaH₂PO₄), calcium hydrogen phosphate (CaHPO₄), iron phosphate dihydrate (FePO₄.2H₂O), magnesium phosphate dibasic trihydrate (MgHPO₄.3H₂O) and phosphorous pentoxide (P₂O₅) (Sigma-

Aldrich, UK). The salt mixture was dried at 350 °C for 30 minutes followed by melting at 1100 °C for 90 minutes, after which the glass was poured directly onto a steel plate and allowed to cool to room temperature. Continuous fibres were produced using an in-house melt-draw fibre spinning [7] facility and traversed onto a Teflon sheet coated drum. Polylactic acid (PLA, PURSORB®PLDL 8038, PURAC, UK) sheets, nonwoven and unidirectional fibre mats used in this study were manufactured via a process detailed in [8]. The PLA sheets were sandwiched alternately with non-woven fibre mats on top and bottom of UD pre-pregs and then placed into 2 mm thick moulds. The layered PLA sheets and fibre mats were then heated to 210 °C for 15 minutes, compressed at 38 bar for 15 minutes and then cooled under a pressure of 38 bar for 15 minutes to room temperature. The resulting laminated composites were sectioned into 45 × 5 × 2 mm samples using a scroll saw and then drilled with 6 screw-holes (2 mm diameter) at specific positions (see Figure 1a). Fixation of the plate on tibia bone was achieved using standard orthopaedic stainless steel screws (see Figures 1b and 1c). The plate samples prepared in this study with their respective sample codes, sample dimensions, volume fractions and sterilisation method are presented in Table 1.

2.3 Burn off Test

The fibre volume fraction of the composite samples was determined via the standard test method (ASTM D 2584 – 94) for ignition loss of cured reinforced resins. The mass of the metal sample tray was measured with and without the composite sample. These samples were then placed into a furnace at 450 °C (below the glass T_g) for an hour, ensuring complete combustion of polymer. The mass of the tray and residue was measured after removal from the furnace.

2.4 Gamma Sterilisation

Gamma Sterilisation of the composites was conducted by Isotron, U.K. The dose applied was 36.7kG, utilising a single cycle.

2.5 Mechanical Testing

2.5.1 Flexural test

1) Flexural test on plate samples

The initial flexural modulus and strength values of the composite specimens were evaluated via three-point bending flexural tests on a Hounsfield Series S testing machine. These tests were conducted in accordance with BS EN ISO 14125:1998. A cross-head speed of 1 mm/min was used at a span of 32mm, with a 1 kN load cell. Flexural studies were conducted using three repeat specimens

2) Flexural test on tibia bone samples

The tibia bone samples were loaded in three-point bending in an Instron testing machine (type 1123 at a constant deformation rate of 5 mm/min with a 5 kN load cell. The span used (40mm) corresponded to the distance between the two outermost screws of the plate, according to the topography of the sample system. Flexural studies were conducted using three repeat specimens. In comparison, properties of stainless steel metal plates (of similar dimensions) and metal plated rabbit tibia bone samples were also examined.

2.5.2 Torsion testing

Tibial bone samples were also loaded in torsion using an Instron testing machine (type 1123) and tested at a constant angular speed rate of 3.6°/min. The gauge length used was 60mm according to the length of the sample system. Torsion tests were conducted using three repeat specimens. In comparison, properties of stainless steel metal plates (of the same dimensions) and metal plated rabbit tibia bone samples were also examined.

2.6 Statistic analysis

Statistical analysis was performed with Tukey's Multiple Comparison Test (95% confidence intervals) via a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), employing GraphPad Prism software (Version 5.01).

3 Results

3.1 Flexural tests on plate samples

The dimensions of the plates investigated were designed according to the rabbit tibia bone

geometry and topography [8]. In addition, all the plates were sterilised using Gamma radiation. This sterilisation technique is the most common method applied to medical implant devices aimed for use *in vivo*. Thus, the effect of incorporating screw-holes and the sterilisation process on the mechanical properties of the composite plate were also investigated (see Figure 1).

3.1.1 PLA plate flexural test

Results from the three-point bend flexural tests on PLA (only) plates (sterilised and non-sterilised and with and without screw-holes) can be seen in Figure 2. Values for these PLA (only) plates ranged between 40-47N and 15-19N/mm for maximum load and stiffness respectively. No significant decrease in maximum load was seen for the non-sterilised and sterilised PLA plate samples, and between the non screw-hole and with screw-holes samples ($P>0.05$). The only significant difference observed was for the stiffness values between the non-sterilised samples with screw-holes and the sterilised samples with no screw-holes ($P<0.05$).

3.2.2 Composite plate flexural test

The mechanical properties of the composite samples were also investigated via three point bend flexural tests and the results are presented in Figure **Error! Reference source not found.**3. The flexural maximum load and stiffness values ranged between 89-118N and 83-118N/mm respectively (for the sterilised and non-sterilised and with and without screw-hole samples). A decrease in stiffness for the non-sterilised samples with no screw-holes compared to sterilised samples with screw-holes ($p<0.05$) was observed. However, no statistically significant difference was observed in maximum load amongst the remainder of the composite plate samples tested ($p>0.05$).

3.2 Flexural tests on bone related samples

Three point bending was also employed to evaluate the mechanical properties (maximum load and stiffness) of the metal and composite plates, intact rabbit tibia bones and tibia bones plated with a metal and composite plate

respectively. These tests were conducted at 40mm span. As seen from Figure 4 below, the flexural maximum load and stiffness properties of the composite plates were significantly lower in comparison to the metal plates. The maximum load and stiffness of the intact rabbit bones were recorded at 536N and 370N/mm respectively. The composite plate properties were approximately 12% of the rabbit tibia bone properties. Whereas, the stiffness of the metal plates were approximately 10 times higher as compared to the composite plates. After plate fixation to the rabbit tibia bone, the metal plate and bone construct properties were significantly higher (58% ($P<0.05$) of maximum load and 199% ($P<0.0001$) of stiffness) in comparison to the intact tibia bone values, respectively. However, the composite plated bone construct revealed only a modest increase of approximately 30% for maximum load and stiffness as compared to the intact tibia bone and these values were not found to be statistically significant ($P>0.05$).

3.3 Torsion tests on bone related samples

Torsional properties of the bone and plated bone constructs are shown in Figure 5. Average maximum torque and failure angles of the intact control bone samples were 34N·m and 25° respectively. No statistically significant difference in failure angles for the bone with six \varnothing 2mm drilled screw-holes, the metal plated bone and composite plated bone constructs ($P>0.05$), in comparison to the intact control bone samples was observed. Regarding the maximum torque properties, the bone with drilled screw-holes, bone with only screws-inserted and the metal plated bone construct revealed a decrease in values as compared to the intact tibia bone values. However, the maximum torque value for the composite plated bone samples revealed a value almost twice that of the metal plated bone construct and were the closest to the maximum torque value of intact bone.

4. Discussion

Bone plate fracture-fixation methods are used to reduce the fracture gap at the fracture site, thus allowing primary bone healing or healing by endosteal callus formation [9]. The role of bone plates and screws is to hold the fractured

bone ends in position without allowing tensile stresses at the fractured interface and to try and induce critical compressive stresses in order to accelerate healing [9]. As such, flexural bending tests were employed in this study due to the actual bending moments exerted *in vivo* which have the tendency to induce both tension and compression stresses across the fracture interface, which can open up the fracture, leading to a reduction in stability of the fixation [10]. Hence, these preliminary biomechanical studies for the newly developed composite bone plates were conducted via three point bending tests with a view to conducting *in vivo* studies to determine the optimal mechanical conditions for the healing of these fractures. As such, both the degree of fixation stiffness *in vitro* and the relative flexural stiffness of the designed composite plates attached to cadaveric rabbit tibia were also investigated.

Figures 2 and 3 illustrate the flexural properties of the neat PLA and PGF reinforced PLA composite plates. For the PLA plates alone, the effect of screw-hole drilling was investigated via comparison between samples with and without screw-holes. The sterilisation effect on the mechanical properties of the plates was illustrated by the flexural results of samples before (non-sterilised) and after (sterilised) gamma irradiation. Both the screw-hole and sterilisation effects on the flexural properties were not found to be statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). The average values of the results for the samples without screw-holes were constantly higher than those for samples with screw-holes. This was suggested to be due to the macro structural changes induced by the stress concentration around the screw-holes caused by the drilling process.

Shubhra et al. investigated the effects of gamma irradiation on the flexural properties of polypropylene (PP) and E-glass reinforced PP composites (which were subjected to a dose range of 0, 2.5, 5 and 10 kilo Gray (kGy)). They reported that the flexural properties of the polymer increased after irradiation up to 5 kGy and decreased after irradiation of 10 kGy. They suggested that this was due to gamma radiation producing free radicals in the polymer. The free radicals could react to change the chemical structure of the polymer by increasing the amount of crosslinks amongst the molecular chains in the polymer thus increasing the physical properties of the materials [11]. In

addition, *Gupta et al.* investigated the effect of gamma radiation on the PLA polymer with exposure at under 1MGy. They found that both scission and cross-linking reactions competed in the PLA polymer under gamma radiation (depending on the dose) [12]. Molecular chain scissions in PLA would cause a decrease in the polymers molecular weight, thus suggesting that a decrease in mechanical properties should follow. However, crosslinking between molecular chains should enhance the polymer's molecular weight and as such its mechanical properties. Thus, the final properties of the PLA product would depend on the degree of crosslinking and scission having occurred after the gamma irradiation process. The results in Figure 2 suggest that the number of PLA polymer chain scissions and cross-linking events were counter-balanced during the gamma sterilisation. Hence, no statistically significant differences were seen.

With regards to the PGF reinforced composite plates, similar profiles to the results of the PLA plates were observed (Figure 3). It has previously been ascertained by *Han et al.* [8] that the screw-hole drilling process did not result in significant damage around the screw-holes in the composite plates due to the utilisation of random fibre mats on the top and bottom of the unidirectional fibre lay-up, which relieved interlaminar delamination and interfilament splitting around the screw holes. In addition, *Shubhra et al.* also stated that the reinforcing fibre inside the polymer matrix was unlikely to be effected by relatively low doses of gamma radiation [11] which led to the composite materials maintaining their mechanical properties after gamma irradiation.

In order to ascertain if the composite plates were mechanically sufficient for fixation of bone for follow-on *in vivo* studies, the mechanical properties of the composite plates, metal plates, intact bones (with no screw-holes) and metal and composite plated bone constructs were compared by testing at the same test span (40mm) and speed (5mm/min). The bending load applied was in the antero-posterior direction, which applied compressive stress in the anterior and tensile stress in the dorsal part of the tibia. This offered, in our test, adequate load directions for the potential situations that may be present *in vivo*. As might be expected, a significantly greater increase in stiffness was observed for the composite plated bone

construct as compared to the intact bone ($P < 0.05$). It should also be noted that the drilling process on the tibiae bone predictably reduced their mechanical properties; which was probably due to damaging the bone structure. However, plate fixation helped to compensate this mechanical loss; and the plated bone construct revealed higher mechanical properties than that of the original intact bone. *Gautier et al* stated that fixation devices take over that portion of the loading which the fractured bone is unable to bear and stabilise the fracture [13].

In general, the flexural bending tests gave a good accordance of the mechanical effects of metal and composite plates fixed to rabbit tibia. However, Figure 5 also showed that the PBG/PLA composite plated bone also revealed better torsional properties than that of the metal plated bone samples and presented the closest torsional properties to that of the intact bone; furthermore, during the experiments, it was found that the screws easily pulled-out from the metal plated bone sample constructs during the torsional tests which was probably due to the large rigidity mismatch between the metal plate and the bone, which resulted in the metal plated bone construct failing in such manner. Conversely, the composite materials were much more flexible under torsional loading compared to the metal plates, which effectively held and assisted the bone and transferred the torsional load to the bone easily during the test. Both bone and composite plate failed at the same time. This showed a more favoured response for utilising the composite plates as compared to the metal plates. *Terjes et al* ascertained that less rigid plates caused less osteoporosis, less stress shielding and less bone loss in the end [14].

A desired requirement for a fixation device is that its mechanical properties are as close as possible to that of the bone itself. One of the main functions and advantages of the resorbable composite implant would be for the mechanical load to be gradually transferred to the bone during the healing process [13].

An *in vivo* study using rabbit tibiae showed that utilisation of rigid (i.e. stainless steel [E 200 GPa] and titanium [E 110 GPa]) plates demonstrated up to 50% strength reduction of the bone after plate removal [15].

To summarise, both flexural and torsional tests suggested that an adequate and more favoured physical support was achieved utilising the composite bone fixation device in comparison to the metal plates.

5 Conclusions

This study showed that drilling of screw-holes and gamma sterilisation did not have a significant effect on the flexural properties of the PLA plates and PBG/PLA composite plates. The utilisation of random mats on top and bottom of the composite fibre layer-up effectively relieved the delamination effect caused by drilling screw-holes into composites containing only unidirectional fibre mats.

The study also indicated that after plate fixation to the rabbit tibia bone, the composite plated bone construct's flexural and torsional properties were closer to the intact bone as compared to the metal plated bone constructs. Suggesting that an adequate and more favoured physical support was achieved utilising the composite bone fixation device in comparison to the metal plates.

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Figures and Table

Figure 1: Samples prepared for biomechanical tests: (a) Designed and manufactured 45x5x2mm PGF/PLA composite bone plate; (b) Standard stainless steel screws; (c) Composite plated rabbit tibia bone.

Figure 2: Max load and flexural stiffness properties comparison of PLA plate samples with and without screw-holes, before and after gamma sterilisation (40mm test span, 1mm/min test speed and 1kNload cell). P represents PLA only, NS is non-sterilised, S represents sterilised and NH and WH represent no screw-holes and with screw-holes respectively.

Figure 3: Max load and flexural stiffness properties comparison of PBG/PLA composite plate samples with and without screw-holes, before and after gamma sterilisation (40mm test span, 1mm/min test speed and 1kN load cell). Here C represents composite plate samples and the remainder is the same as the caption in Figure 2.

Figure 4: Flexural properties of implant plates and plated tibia samples via three point bending flexural tests (utilising 40mm test span, 5mm/min test speed and 5kN load cell).

Figure.5. Torsional properties of the plated tibia samples under torsion test (60mm gauge length, 3.6°/min test speed).

Figure.6. Failure mode of PLA plate and composite plate after 3 point bending test with 32mm span, 1mm/min and 1kN load cell

Table 1 Sample codes with sample dimension, screw-hole structure, including sterilisation method and actual volume fraction V_f .

Sample Group	Sample Code	Sample Dimension	Screw-holes	Sterilisation Method	V_f (%)
PLA Plate	P-NS-NH	45x5x2mm	0	N/A	0
	P-NS-WH	45x5x2mm	6	N/A	0
	P-S-NH	45x5x2mm	0	Gamma	0
	P-S-WH	45x5x2mm	6	Gamma	0
Composite Plate	C-NS-NH	45x5x2mm	0	N/A	46.7±1.4
	C-NS-WH	45x5x2mm	6	N/A	46.7±1.4
	C-S-NH	45x5x2mm	0	Gamma	46.7±1.4
	C-S-WH	45x5x2mm	6	Gamma	46.7±1.4

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